

Supplementary Information:
Dissecting complex nanoparticle heterostructures
via multimodal data fusion with
aberration-corrected STEM spectroscopy

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Mathematical details

PCA Analysis

In this section, we provide a more detailed description of the PCA analysis performed in the manuscript

A data tensor $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_E \times N_x \times N_y}$ containing either the pre-processed EELS or EDX data is first matricized by unfolding the spatial modes. This reduces spatial dimension of the data to one, where $N_{\text{px}} = N_x \times N_y$ denotes the total number of pixels, resulting in $\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_E \times N_{\text{px}}}$ where each column vector represents the spectra taken at the corresponding pixel position. The data matrix is subsequently centered by subtracting out the spectral mean yielding $\mathbf{Y}_c = \mathbf{Y} - \frac{1}{N_{\text{px}}} \mathbf{Y} \mathbf{1}_{N_{\text{px}}}$ where $\mathbf{1}_{N_{\text{px}}}$ represents a column vector of ones having dimensions $N_{\text{px}} \times 1$.

From the transposed, centered matrix, the singular values are computed with singular value decomposition (SVD)

$$\mathbf{Y}_c^T = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^T \quad (1)$$

where the columns of $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_E \times N_E}$ contain the principal axes (spectra), $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_E \times N_{\text{px}}}$ contains the singular values along the diagonal, and the columns of $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{px}} \times N_{\text{px}}}$ contain the weights of the principal spectra projected onto the raw data. The SVD is closely related to the covariance matrix of the centered data

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C} &= \frac{1}{N_{\text{px}} - 1} \mathbf{Y}_c^T \mathbf{Y}_c = \\ &= \frac{\mathbf{V} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^T}{N_{\text{px}} - 1} = \mathbf{V} \frac{\mathbf{\Sigma}^2}{N_{\text{px}} - 1} \mathbf{V}^T \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

which is equivalent to first computing \mathbf{C} and then diagonalizing it via eigenvalue decomposition.

Data Fusion

The output of the linking action in low-level data fusion is the concatenated matrix \mathbf{F} containing the variance-stabilized raw data. Thus, $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x \times N_y \times N_{E,f}}$ and $N_{E,f}$ is the number of spectral channels (variables) in the concatenated data block. For this experiment, $N_{E,f} = N_{E,1} + N_{E,2}$. As discussed in the manuscript, a data block weighting is necessary prior to matrix concatenation. Our proposed approach is presented in equation 3

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{w_1}{\theta_1} \\ \frac{w_2}{\theta_2} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{w_m}{\theta_m} \end{bmatrix} \otimes \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Y}_1 \\ \mathbf{Y}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{Y}_m \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where θ_m is a scalar representing the variance of \mathbf{Y}_m , w_m is an arbitrary weight applied to each raw data block, m describes the modality, and \otimes is the Kronecker product.

The ratio $\frac{w_m}{\theta_m}$ is chosen for convenience to provide a more intuitive understanding of the weighting process. θ_m is a scalar for each \mathbf{Y}_m defined as

$$\theta_m = \|\mathbf{Y}_m\|_{\text{F}}^2 \quad (4)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_{\text{F}}^2$ represents the Frobenius norm. Alternatively, if a reasonable estimate of the rank of \mathbf{Y}_m is available, θ_m can be the sum of the first k eigenvalues. This will yield a slightly more intuitive interpretation of the weights.

Following fusion, SVD is performed on \mathbf{F} using equation 2. The resulting decomposition includes a matrix of shared variables $\mathbf{U} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{E,f} \times N_{E,f}}$, which can be split into the two original modalities. Note that the score matrix $\mathbf{V} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{\text{px}} \times N_{\text{px}}}$ and the singular values $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{N_{E,f} \times N_{\text{px}}}$ both share spatial factors between modalities and hence cannot be split. Thus the fractional

variance described by each individual component for each modality $f_{k,m}$ was estimated as

$$f_{k,m} = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{\|\mathbf{U}_{i,m} \Sigma_i \mathbf{V}_i^T\|_F}{\|\mathbf{Y}_{c,m}\|_F}. \quad (5)$$

Equation 5 was used to create figure 3 in the manuscript.

The Linear Mixing Model and QMV-NMF

A common assumption in hyperspectral imaging is that the experimental dataset can be described as a linear combination of a smaller number of latent spectra that are mixed in an unknown amount within the hyperspectral scene. The model describing this assumption is often referred to as the Linear Mixing Model (LMM) and it is mathematically formalized as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{AS} + \mathbf{N}. \quad (6)$$

In eq. 6, \mathbf{Y} represents the matricized and centered raw data, exactly as in equation 1. The matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_E \times p}$ contains p source spectra, commonly referred to in the literature as "endmembers", as column vectors. Matrix $\mathbf{S} \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times N_{px}}$ describes the distribution of the p endmembers across the N_{px} pixels of the hyperspectral dataset. Finally, $\mathbf{N} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_E \times N_{px}}$ represents the matrix containing all of the data variance that is not described by the outer product of \mathbf{AS} . Adopting the terminology of Bioucas-Dias *et al.*,¹ \mathbf{S} is referred to as the "abundance maps," \mathbf{A} is referred to as a "mixing matrix," which contains p "endmembers" representing the pure spectral signatures of the hyperspectral scene. For a well chosen number of endmembers p , \mathbf{N} will contain mostly noise and artifacts that do not influence the physical interpretation of the data model.

Equation 6 essentially describes a generalized linear regression of p variables on the predictor matrix \mathbf{S} . Although very similar to equation 1, it differs in a few key aspects. First, the goal of PCA is the estimation of \mathbf{V} , which is accomplished via eigenvalue decomposition

of the data covariance matrix. This is both algebraically deterministic and guaranteed to provide an optimal fit of the model to the raw data for k principal components in a least squares sense. However, the principal components themselves do not necessarily reflect the physics of the system and are thus difficult to directly interpret. In contrast, the LMM of equation 6 can use any combination of source spectra desired. The contents of matrices \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{S} are moreover commonly estimated using matrix factorization methods, permitting constraints to be placed on the data model to reflect the physics of the investigated system. Although this is an inherently stochastic approach, it is possible to cast this as a convex optimization problem.

In this work, we exploit the mixing geometry of the dataset to achieve our estimates of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{S} . The justification for this approach is based on the assumption that, due to the spectral mixing (arising from the projective geometry of the hyperspectral dataset), there are no "pure" endmembers present in the raw data. However, the data are sufficiently distributed to reveal the facets of the data simplex. The geometry can be revealed by first reducing the dimensionality of the full, fused dataset \mathbf{F} via PCA and choosing an appropriate rank for the data model. The first $p - 1$ components are subsequently projected onto the centered matrix \mathbf{F}_c . In this projection, it is known that the data assume the form of a p -dimensional simplex in affine space. Critically, the vertices of this simplex are assumed to lie outside of the data subspace itself.

The estimation of endmembers is non-trivial and heavily dependent on the population density of the signal subspace (SSS). In this paper, we focus on using the Nonnegative matrix factorization quadratic minimum volume (NMF-QMV) approach.² This approach seeks to minimize the following objective function

$$\begin{aligned} \arg \min_{\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{S}} \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{AS} - \mathbf{Y}\|_{\mathbf{F}}^2 + \beta V(\mathbf{A}) \\ \text{subject to: } \mathbf{S} \geq \mathbf{0}, \quad \mathbf{1}_p^{\mathbf{T}} \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{1}_{N_{px}}^{\mathbf{T}} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where $V(\mathbf{A})$ represents the volume of the simplex whose vertices are defined by the columns

of \mathbf{A} . The first term $\|\mathbf{AS} - \mathbf{Y}\|_F^2$ essentially measures the residuals between the data model \mathbf{AS} and the raw data \mathbf{Y} via the Frobenius norm and thus serves to minimize reconstruction errors. The constraint of non-negativity and sum-to-one are applied to the abundance maps \mathbf{S} . The regularization parameter β is used to control the trade-off between the two competing objective arguments. The strategy for its optimization adopted in this work is outlined in detail in Zhuang *et al.*² Once the mixing matrix \mathbf{A} is estimated, \mathbf{S} can be estimated sparse unmixing by variable splitting and augmented Lagrangian (SUnSAL) algorithm³ subject to the constraints outlined in equation 7.

Additional experimental results

PCA model

Figure S1: PCA model produced from the core-loss EELS datablock (a), the raw EDX datablock (b) and the EDX data block after inpainting many of the missing values by applying a smoothing filter (c).

Figure S1a shows the scree plot for the SVD decomposition on the core-loss EELS dataset. We observe that most of the variance of the dataset is captured within the first 6 components. Additional components largely describe the additive noise response. The assumption of an additive noise model is valid for homoscedastic data, which was achieved in this case through

application of the generalized Amscombe transformation.^{4,5}

The scree plot for the raw EDX data is presented in figure S1b. Here, we observe that only one meaningful component is retrieved, which essentially describes the variation in total x-ray emission cross-section. It is therefore not useful for describing the chemical heterogeneity of this system. This is a consequence of the sparse nature of the EDX dataset, as discussed in the manuscript.

Application of spatio-spectral blurring to the EDX data before PCA decomposition improves the ability for the PCA model to describe the variance of the EDX data block. The scree plot for this is shown in figure S1c. Here, we find at least three and maybe even five meaningful components to describe the data. For the proposed data fusion approach in the manuscript, we used this "blurred" dataset to ensure inclusion of components that are distinct to the EDX data block into both the PCA and QMV-NMF models.

Figure S2a shows the results of PCA decomposition on the core-loss EELS data block as well as the EDX data block. We observe strong spatially-correlated variations in the score maps as well as clear spectral components for the first four components. Components 5 and 6 appear very weak, but describe slight modifications to the O and Co ELNES in the edge regions of this catalyst. We believe that this is caused by the presence of a SiO_x -rich impurity phase. These components are included in the data fusion model.

Figure S2b shows the results of the weighted PCA decomposition on the raw EDX data. We clearly see that the only meaningful component is the first one, and that this largely describes variations of the spectral mean. Components 2 - 6 (as well as the remainder) only describe noise. This demonstrates the poor explanatory power provided by raw PCA decomposition.

Figure S2c presents the results of a PCA decomposition following spatio-spectral blurring. While the spatial resolution is clearly degraded, we observe that the first 3 components describe chemically meaningful information in this dataset. Component 2 appears to describe the surface or edge of this region and is likely closely related to components 2, 5, and 6 for

Figure S2: PCA model produced from the core-loss EELS datablock (a), the raw EDX datablock (b) and the EDX data block after inpainting many of the missing values by applying a smoothing filter (c).

the core-loss EELS dataset. Component 3 does not have a similar component in the EELS data and is therefore considered to be distinct. It is included in the data fusion approach by appropriate data block weighting.

EDX inpainting model using data fusion

Figure S3 presents the PCA model for the EDX generated on the fused data blocks using $w_2 = 0.25$. The raw EDX data are plotted in light gray in the background while the PCA model is presented in dark red. On the left, the summation window (in number of pixels) is presented. The EDX maps on the top denote the regions from which the summations were

Figure S3: Comparison between the raw EDX data (light gray) and the PCA model (dark red) derived from decomposition of the fused EELS and EDX data blocks. The y-axis denotes total number of counts. The EDX maps for $S-K_{\alpha}$ and $P-K_{\alpha}$ are shown to highlight the significance of the summation regions.

extracted. These maps were chosen to highlight compositional features of interest in this sample. The left column of graphs was extracted from the S-rich impurity phase and serves to demonstrate that this weak feature is still detected in the PCA model. The right column of graphs was centered on the pixel shown in figure 1b of the manuscript.

For a single pixel, we observe very few EDX counts, highlighting the extreme sparsity

of the EDX data block. Despite this, we observe that the PCA model attempts to fill in the missing values. These values are derived from linear combinations of the principal components, which have been estimated on the fused dataset. Their scaling to the EDX data, therefore, is largely achieved through their fit with the EELS data block.

Since the ground truth is not known in this case, we attempt to verify the model by examining what happens to both the model as well as the raw data when we sum over increasingly larger spatial regions. We observe that, regardless of which region we investigate, the fit between the PCA model and the raw EDX data becomes quite good for large summations. When fewer pixels are sampled, the fit is still reasonable within the tolerance of the sparse data.

Alternative unmixing results

In this section, we include the unmixing results for various attempts.

Figure S4 shows the unmixing results if the vertex describing endmember 5 is not set to the value estimated from VCA. In this case, endmember 5 is estimated to be outside of the dataset. This is not a good assumption since a very large number of datapoints in the hyperspectral scene describe this background contribution without any mixing from the catalyst material (and, hence, any other endmembers). Consequently, the extrapolation of this vertex outside the data space results in a non-physical result including negative intensities on the endmember spectra for both EDX and EELS. Despite this, the results from the other endmembers are nearly identical to what is observed if this vertex is constrained to remain within the dataset. For this reason, we do not believe that this impacts the conclusions of the manuscript.

Figure S5 presents the unmixing results when the number of estimated endmembers is set to $p = 6$. We observe an additional sparse endmember (endmember 1 in this case) that does not contribute to the explanatory power of the model. The abundance map does not contain spatially-correlated information and the retrieved spectra closely resemble

Figure S4: Unmixing results when the vertex for endmember 5 is not manually set to the value derived from VCA.

Figure S5: Unmixing results when $p = 6$ endmembers are presumed

those of endmember 3. For this reason, we argue that the addition of more endmembers produces an unmixing model that overfits the data and, thus, is less reliable than the one presented in the manuscript. Despite this, we note that, since these experiments do not have access to the "ground truth," it is worth presenting these results for discussion and consideration. Sparse abundance maps as a potential sign for superfluous endmembers is a topic that has been explored in the literature. The robust collaborative non-negative matrix factorization algorithm published by Li *et al.*⁶ seeks to exploit this observation by adding an additional term to the volume minimization objective function to penalize overfitting and, hence, additionally provide a more robust estimate of p . We did not employ this approach in our work here, rather basing our estimation of p on a simple scree-plot estimate and the subsequent inspection of results when p is increased.

Figure S6 presents the unmixing results if the pre-edge background is removed prior to application of QMV-NMF. We observe largely the same result as the case presented in the manuscript where the pre-edge background is included. However, a few small variations in the EDX impurity peaks are observed. Endmember 2 in this representation includes some of the P signal in EDX, while endmember 3 includes some Si. We justify our inclusion of the pre-edge background based on the work of Muto *et al.*, who discuss this in great detail.⁷ They observe that the removal of the pre-edge background results in zero and negative entries, degrading the validity of the non-negativity constraint. They also observe a reduction in the signal to noise ratio of the resulting abundance maps. Comparison between figure S6 and figure 5 in this manuscript is consistent with this previously reported observation.

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Figure S6: Unmixing results when the pre-edge background is removed prior to QMV-NMF

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